

A Symmetric Two-way Parallel Division Algorithm

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Abstract

For those divisors ending with digits 1, 3, 7, and 9 in the ones place, this paper presents a new division algorithm without using any divisions. Only addition and multiplication are performed during the calculation process of this new algorithm. The quotient is the digit in the ones place of the results of each step addition and it can be obtained without using trial division. In addition, the new algorithm does not follow the traditional division principle. And compared to the traditional division, the new division algorithm is much simpler and easier. Besides, this new algorithm division can be calculated from two directions simultaneously and the calculation process is also symmetric. Thus, division can also be calculated in a parallel way, providing a new idea for the parallel computing of division by quantum computers in the future.

Keywords: parallel division, inverse division algorithm, quantum computer

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1 Introduction

1.1 A new division algorithm without using any division

For thousands of years, the division algorithms have always followed the idea that dividends must be divided by the divisor. Based on our long-time research, we found that as long as the divisors ending in digits 1, 3, 7, and 9 in the ones place, there is another division algorithm that is much simpler and easier than the traditional one. And it does not even follow the traditional division principle. The new division algorithm can be calculated from two directions simultaneously, thus makes the parallel computation of division possible. This is what modern computers desire in the multi-core era, and it is also a necessary division algorithm for future quantum computers. The new algorithm indicates that the division can also be carried out according to a certain rule and does not necessarily follow the basic principle of dividing the dividend by the divisor. With a deeper understanding of the division by human beings, there will be more new division algorithms. Actually, there are as many as eleven algorithms that perform the calculation from back to front.

1.2 The theoretical basis of the new division algorithm

According to the basic theory of number theory, any natural number can be uniquely expressed as $2^\alpha \cdot 5^\beta \cdot d$, $(d, 10) = 1$. The digit in the ones place of d must only be 1, 3, 7, 9, and $c \div d$ (Generally, it is supposed that $c < d$. If it is not, perform the division again to achieve $c < d$.) must be a purely cyclic decimal [1].The new division algorithm is achieved based on this principle of pure cyclic decimals. And the new algorithm requires calculating one loop before it is completed.

$$\begin{aligned}
 1 &= 0.142857 \times 7 + 0.000001 = 0.999999 + 0.000001 \\
 3 &= 2.999997 + 0.000003 = 0.428571 \times 7 + 0.000003 \\
 3 \div 7 &= 0.428571 + 0.000003 \div 7 \\
 3 \div 7 &= 21 \div 49 \\
 21 + 0.428571 &= 21.428571 = 0.428571 \times 50 + 0.000021 \\
 21.428571 \div 50 &= 0.428571 + 0.000021 \div 50 \dots
 \end{aligned}$$

That is the reason why it can duplicate the quotient to the dividend when division $21 \div 50$ is used to calculate division $21 \div 49$. Let’s take the calculation of $3 \div 7$ as an example to illustrate this new algorithm. Let $a = 3$, $b = 7$, calculate $a \div b = ?$

2 Division Algorithms

2.1 Calculating from front to back

2.1.1 The algorithm of calculating from front to back and the calculation rules of the new divisor and dividend

The new algorithm is performed by making appropriate alterations to the divisors and dividends and then calculating the new divisors and dividends. The calculation methods are different for those divisors ending with digits 1, 3, 7, and 9 in the ones place. The calculation rule of the new divisor is (take 412 divided by 621, 623, 627, 629 for examples):

$$412 \div 621 \text{ turns into } 412 \times 9 \div (621 \times 9 + 1) = 3708 \div 5590 = 370.8 \div 559$$

$$412 \div 623 \text{ turns into } 412 \times 3 \div (623 \times 3 + 1) = 1236 \div 1870 = 123.6 \div 187$$

$$412 \div 627 \text{ turns into } 412 \times 7 \div (627 \times 7 + 1) = 2884 \div 4390 = 288.4 \div 459$$

$$412 \div 629 \text{ turns into } 412 \times 1 \div (629 \times 1 + 1) = 412 \div 630 = 41.2 \div 63$$

In the example $3 \div 7$, the new dividend is turned into $a_1 = 3 \times 7 = 21$, the new divisor is turned into $b_1 = 7 \times 7 + 1 = 50$, and the division formula is turned into $a_1 \div b_1 = 21 \div 50 = 2.1 \div 5$.

2.1.2 Process of calculating from front to back

$$\begin{array}{r} 0. ? \\ 5 \overline{) 2. 1} \end{array} \quad (1)$$

The “?” in division formula (1) represents the position that the new quotient is to be copied to the dividend.

$$\begin{array}{r} 0. 4 ? \\ 5 \overline{) 2. 1 4 ?} \\ \underline{20} \\ 14 ? \end{array} \quad (2)$$

Quotient 4 in division formula (2) is copied to the ones place of the dividend. Subtract 20 (5 times 4) from 21. The “?” after the remainder 14 indicates the position where the next quotient appears. The quotient is copied from the divisor to the ones place of the dividend, then appears to the right of 14 after subtraction.

$$\begin{array}{r} 0. 4 2 ? \\ 5 \overline{) 2. 1 4 2 ?} \\ \underline{20} \\ 14 \\ \underline{10} \\ 42 ? \end{array} \quad (3)$$

The calculation method for the latter digits is exactly the same as the calculation method for the quotient of the first two digits.

$$\begin{array}{r}
 0.428? \\
 5 \overline{) 2.1428?} \\
 \underline{20} \\
 14 \\
 \underline{10} \\
 42 \\
 \underline{40} \\
 28?
 \end{array} \tag{4}$$

$$\begin{array}{r}
 0.428571 \\
 5 \overline{) 2.1428571} \\
 \underline{20} \\
 14 \\
 \underline{10} \\
 42 \\
 \underline{40} \\
 28 \\
 \underline{25} \\
 35 \\
 \underline{35} \\
 07 \\
 \underline{5} \\
 21
 \end{array} \tag{5}$$

When the remainder appears number 21 again, it means that the calculation of one loop is completed. Repeat the loops and no more calculations are needed. $3 \div 7 = 0.428571 \dots$

2.2 Calculating from back to front (hereinafter referred to as inverse algorithm)

The inverse algorithms can be divided into two categories: one requires recalculation of the divisor and dividend, while the other does not.

2.2.1 Calculation rules for new divisor and dividend

Let $a_1 = 3 \times 7 = 21$, $b_1 = (7 \times 7 + 1) \div 10 = 5$. It is a little different from calculating from front to back, because in the first step of the inverse algorithm the dividend has to be cut off one digit, which is equivalent to dividing by 10, the new divisor calculation should be divided by 10 accordingly. In the example, $a_1 \div b_1 = 21 \div 50$ turns into $a_1 \div b_1 = 21 \div 5$.

2.2.2 The calculating process of the inverse algorithm

$$\begin{array}{r} \overline{2 \underline{1}} (5 \end{array} \quad (6)$$

The underscore in division formula (6) is to indicate that the digit is to be moved to the quotient position.

$$\begin{array}{r} \frac{1}{\overline{2 \underline{1}} (5 \end{array} \quad (7)$$

The number 1 in division formula (7) is moved to the quotient position as the first quotient of the inverse algorithm.

$$\begin{array}{r} \frac{1}{\overline{2 \underline{1}} (5 \\ + \underline{5} \\ \hline 0 \underline{7} \end{array} \quad (8)$$

Division formula (8) is the second step. Number 5 times 1 then plus 2 is equal to 7. Note that the step there is subtraction in section 2.1.2 process of calculating from front to back, while here is addition correspondingly. Because the number 7 is about to move to the quotient position, there is no digit before number 7. To avoid making mistakes when performing the addition, add a number 0 before the number 7.

$$\begin{array}{r} \frac{7 \ 1}{\overline{2 \underline{1}} (5 \\ + \underline{5} \\ \hline 0 \underline{7} \end{array} \quad (9)$$

The number 7 with the underscore in division formula (9) is moved to the quotient position.

$$\begin{array}{r} \frac{7 \ 1}{\overline{2 \underline{1}} (5 \\ + \underline{5} \\ \hline + 3 \ \frac{0 \ 7}{\underline{5}} \\ \hline 3 \ \underline{5} \end{array} \quad (10)$$

In division formula (10), number 5 times 7 plus 0. Number 5 is to move to the quotient position. The algorithm for the following digits is the same until the dividend appears number 21 again. Then return to the beginning, thus one loop of calculation is completed. The following calculation is the second loop and repeats the above process, as shown in division formula (11).

$$\begin{array}{r}
0.428571 \\
\hline
21 \overline{)5} \\
+5 \\
\hline
07 \\
+35 \\
\hline
35 \\
+25 \\
\hline
28 \\
+40 \\
\hline
42 \\
+10 \\
\hline
14 \\
+20 \\
\hline
21
\end{array} \tag{11}$$

Since it is an inverse calculation, the number “0” must be added at the end. The calculation method for number 0 is the same as other numbers. Move 0 to the quotient position. Because 0 times any number equals 0, just move one digit backward to continue the calculation.

2.2.3 The inverse algorithm by cutting 0 that without recalculating the divisor and the dividend

From the above two calculation processes, it can be seen that calculating from front to back and calculating from back to front are symmetric, copy and cut are symmetric and addition and subtraction are symmetric, which fully reflect the rigor and grace of mathematical logic.

Naturally, it will be thought that whether there will be a symmetric algorithm for ordinary division or not. The ordinary division is calculated from left to right. After each step of the calculation, the dividend should be multiplied by 10 and then continue the calculation. It can also be considered as adding a number 0. Thus according to the symmetry, the algorithm calculating from back to the front should cut off a number 0 for every calculation of the digits, meanwhile, turn subtraction into addition. Is this conjecture correct? After repeated calculations and tests, we found this symmetric algorithm. Mathematics is so beautiful and exciting.

Let’s take $34 \div 73$ as an example to illustrate the division algorithm by cutting 0. It is a symmetric algorithm for ordinary division, and there is no need to recalculate the divisor and dividend. Let $a = 34$, $b = 73$, $a \div b = 34 \div 73 = 0.46575342$, and the calculation process of the inverse algorithm by cutting 0 is shown in division formula (12).

$$\begin{array}{r}
0.46575342 \\
\hline
34 \overline{)73} \\
+146 \\
\hline
180 \\
+292 \\
\hline
310 \\
+219 \\
\hline
250 \\
+365 \\
\hline
390 \\
+511 \\
\hline
550 \\
+365 \\
\hline
420 \\
+438 \\
\hline
480 \\
+292 \\
\hline
340
\end{array} \tag{12}$$

The first quotient in division formula (12) is determined like this: from number 1, 2, 3 . . . to number 9, try one by one to multiply by the digit 3 in the ones place of number 73. Then add the digit 4 in the ones place of number 34. Only $2 \times 3 + 4 = 10$, which satisfies the requirement that the digit in the ones place of the sum must be equal to 0. Therefore, the first quotient can only take number 2. Similarly, the second quotient is 4, because only $4 \times 3 + 8 = 20$, which makes the digit in the ones place of the sum 20 is number 0.

The rule for determining the quotient in the new algorithm is as follows. The quotient times the digit in the tens place of the divisor, then plus the digit in the tens place of the dividend. Besides, the digit in the tens place of the sum must be equal to zero.

2.2.4 Nine other inverse algorithms without recalculating the divisor and dividend

In the calculation process of the inverse algorithm in section 2.2.2, the digits cut off at each step in the tens place are not necessarily the same, while in the inverse algorithm by cutting 0 in section 2.2.3, the digits cut off at each step in the tens place are exactly the same. All of them were number 0.

In addition to the above two algorithms, there are nine other different inverse algorithms by cutting off number 1, 2, . . . , 9. These nine numbers can all be the first digit to be cut off in the first step of the inverse algorithms. From the second step, the number cut off in each step of the calculation process is the same, which can either be number 0 or number 9. Therefore, the result of a division can be calculated by ten different inverse algorithms, among which cutting off number 0 is the simplest and easiest. The other nine algorithm are similar to this inverse algorithms by cutting off number 0, so they are omitted here.

3 Discussion

3.1 Comparison of the efficiency of the new algorithm with other algorithms

Compared to the twelve new division algorithms mentioned above, the inverse algorithm in section 2.2.2 is the fastest and easiest. Although it is one step more than the inverse algorithm by cutting off number 0 in section 2.2.3 for calculating the new divisor and dividend, it saves the trial calculation of each quotient, which is much faster and much easier. The algorithm also has the following benefits:

First, as long as one loop is finished, the calculation accuracy of the digit in any place can be obtained.

Second, there is another advantage of the inverse algorithm. The latter digits in one number can be calculated directly without calculating the former digits first, which can meet some special requirements.

Third, for the divisors as 19, 29, 39, \dots , 89, the division turns from two digits into one digit, which can easily be done mentally.

Fourth, it is convenient for dual or multi-core computers to perform parallel computation. One process computes from the front to the back, while the other computes from the back to the front. The computation ends when they meet or it finishes at the specific place respectively.

3.2 The relationship between “Yi Xiang Tian Kai Chu Fa” and the new division algorithm

The famous Chinese mathematics popular science writer Mr. Xiangbai Tan named this division algorithm in which the quotient is copied to the dividend position as “Yi Xiang Tian Kai Chu Fa” (the whimsical division) [2]. The famous mathematician Von Neumann replaced the traditional division $1 \div 19$ with this novel and whimsical division $0.1 \div 2$ that with a time delay of the quotient [2, 227]. However, the algorithm he used at the time can only be performed for the divisions where the dividend is 1, and the divisors are 19, 29, 39, \dots , 79, 89 these eight specific two-digit numbers. Actually, these eight numbers are just a few special cases of the countless numbers calculated by the inverse division algorithm calculating from front to back which is invented by us. The inner principle of how these eight numbers can be calculated in this way is explained by this paper.

3.3 Shortcomings of the new division algorithm

It should be noted that the new division algorithm cannot be applied to calculate the divisors ending with the digits 0, 2, 5 in the ones place. Therefore, the new division algorithm is not a negation or replacement of traditional division, but a sort of development and supplement for traditional division. The most important is that the algorithm is a new thinking way of division performing from serial computation to parallel computation.

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References

- [1] C.-D. Pan and C.-B. Pan, *Chu Deng Shu Lun [Elementary Number Theory]*, 2nd ed. Peking University Press, 2003, ISBN: 7-301-06075-9.
- [2] X.-B. Tan, *Le Zai Qi Zhong De Shu Xue [Happiness within Mathematics]*. Science Press, 2005, ISBN: 7-03-015762-1.